

TRAIN4EU

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agendas and support in 4EU+

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common research agenda**

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Deliverable Overview

Deliverable title:	Report on transformative change potential and piloting, common research agenda
Work Package:	WP 1 Developing a common research agenda [Months: 1-35] / University of Milan
Deliverable summary:	<p>D1.3 – <i>Report on transformative change potential and piloting, common research agenda</i> describes the co-learning efforts undertaken across all universities, using both positive and negative lessons learned in T1.2. (See D1.2 / M14)</p> <p>The deliverable outlines the results of shared analyses and ideas co-developed for new innovative approaches to create common research agendas. Based on the assessments, a set of potential pilot transformative actions was identified and co-designed. Among these, a pilot action was selected for piloting and implemented.</p> <p>The deliverable also focuses on the collaboration with selected stakeholders (e.g., other European Universities Alliances, EARMA, national networks and association of research managers and administrators).</p> <p>Finally, the deliverable provides a discussion of WP1 outcomes' embedment into the 4EU+ structures and activities.</p>
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1. Introduction

WP1 – *Developing a Common Research Agenda* aimed at building a shared agenda and integrated plan on research among the 4EU+ partners by identifying best practices across the Alliance and designing a set of piloting transformative actions.

Under Task 1.2. the six partner universities analysed and assessed in-depth the four cases identified under Task 1.1. and illustrated in D1.1: *Research Support Services* (M6) (especially pre- and post-award) as key expertise and drivers for transformative pilot actions; *Digital Transformation/Artificial Intelligence* and *Sustainability/Green Deal* as two thematic cases and *Interdisciplinarity* as cross-thematic case.

The outcomes of Task 1.2. activities and analyses allowed to single out a set of potential transformative actions outlined in D1.2. Relatively to *Research Services*, the area of informing/training researchers was deemed as promisingly transformative. Concerning the two thematic cases, *Digital Transformation/Artificial Intelligence* and *Sustainability/Green Deal*, the organisation of dedicated thematic events (e.g., a combination of info-sessions on available calls and proper exchange sessions) was considered as a first possible direction to design joint actions. With respect to the cross-thematic case *Interdisciplinarity*, no specific area of transformation was suggested as, by definition, the interdisciplinarity perspective will be considered and employed in the design of each pilot action.

For Task 1.3, the WP1 team, in light of both positive and negative lessons learned from Task 1.2 and outlined in D1.2 (M14), shared more in-depth analyses of each partner university's best practices to find common ground to developing and co-design pilot transformative actions (Section 3). As a result of the first phase of co-designing, a first pilot action was implemented (November 8, 2022): an online informative and networking meeting, Net4Res-Green Transitions, addressed to all researchers of the 4EU+ community and with a focus on HE funding opportunities related to Sustainability (Section 4).

After that, the WP1 Team started a second phase of co-designing of the pilot actions, taking into considerations the outcomes and results of the first attempt. Also -and in accordance with Subtask 1.3.2— the WP1 Team focused on the selection of stakeholders across the partner countries to gather further inspiration for innovative and transformative actions for the development of a shared research agenda. Section 5 reports in detail the results of this subtask. Section 6 finally concludes with a reflection on WP1 outcomes' anchoring within the 4EU+ Alliance structures and activities.

2. Workplan and organisational arrangements

As foreseen in D1.2 and according to Subtask 1.3.1, the first months of Task 1.3 (M15-M21) were dedicated to the analyses of potential transformative areas identified in D1.2 and to the co-designing of the related potential pilot actions. WP1 Team had a general online meeting monthly, accompanied by occasional bilateral meetings when necessary (e.g., for the mapping and analyses of universities' internal best practices to be considered as examples for the co-designing of joint pilot actions).

M21-M25 were dedicated to the implementation of a first pilot action (M23) and to its following outcomes' evaluation. All preparation and follow up took place through online meetings which included colleagues external to the WP1 Team (e.g., 4EU+ Communication Officers, IT expert officer).

M25-M35 were simultaneously addressed to refining the list of pilot actions and to collaboration with other stakeholders to gather further inspiration for innovative and transformative actions for the development of a shared research agenda (e.g., other European Universities Alliances, EARMA, other research management associations and networks). The WP1 Team was represented in two face-to-face synergy meetings (M26 and M29) organized in collaboration with other European Universities Alliances and the Italian Network of Research Manager and Administrators. Finally, substantial focus was devoted to the embedding of WP1 activities and outcomes within the 4EU+ Alliance structures and agenda.

3. Table of potential pilot actions

During M15-M20, the results outlined in D1.2. were further discussed and integrated to develop a more structured list of possible joint pilot actions. Each university was asked to undergo an internal mapping of past or ongoing activities and initiatives which could serve as an example or a basis to design joint actions considering the three main transformative areas illustrated below.

As mentioned in the introduction, starting from the cases individuated in D1.1. and the list outlined in D1.2., the designing of pilot actions was directed toward three main transformative areas: the informing/training of researchers, the organisation of dedicated thematic events (info-sessions on calls; exchange sessions) and the cross-cutting area of interdisciplinarity.

3.1 Criteria for the designing of pilot actions

For each area of transformation, different types of possible pilot action were jointly discussed. Two general criteria were adopted in approaching the designing phase:

1. avoiding duplication of already existing efforts within universities. This is why the first internal step of gathering detailed information concerning current and planned activities at each university was deemed necessary;
2. avoiding overlapping with ongoing or future initiatives in the domain of other WPs (especially WP2-5). Both criteria served the purpose of maximising the specific added-value of 4EU+ and WP1 joint actions vis-à-vis activities in place while, at the same time, containing workload and use of resources.

For each action, then, some specific criteria were adopted to have a complete and coherent design. Besides being assigned to an area of transformation, every action should have well specified:

- (Area of transformation)
- Target: who is the targeted group of the initiative/event? (4EU+ community, 4EU+ researchers, 4EU+ early career researchers, 4EU+ senior researchers, etc.)
- Content: what should they expect from joining/participating? (information, materials, support, networking etc.)
- Modality: where does the event take place? (online/hybrid/face-to-face.)
- Participation: how to participate? (free participation, free participation with pre-registration, internal selection of participants etc.)
- Funding: are funding necessary for the initiative? (yes/no)

Both general and specific criteria were used as guidelines throughout the work on the table of potential pilot actions presented and reported below.

3.2 Table of Pilot Actions

The below table has been re-discussed and further refined over the months with the present version being completed in M33. In the Area of Transformation of Training/Informing researchers – especially related to the Research Services case – a possible pilot action was individuated in the setting up of a series of training sessions on selected topics and transversal skills. The targeted group for these trainings could be the entire 4EU+ community, meaning both 4EU+ early career and senior researchers and 4EU+ research support officers. The relevance and actuality of the topics selected in fact makes this sort of trainings potentially helpful also for the research managers and administrators and would be a coherent step to comply with the ERA Action 17 objectives.

The topics temporarily selected are emergent issues that permeate nowadays debate on research: Foreign Interference in Research, Export control & Data Dual Use, Data Security, Research and Researchers Assessment, Gender in Research, (Open Science), (Citizen Science)¹. These trainings could be held online, so to possibly ensure and stand a high participation rate and would not require specific funding so to make the pilot action both feasible, replicable and sustainable.

In the same Area of Transformation, another potential pilot action was individuated in the organisation of a “4EU+ School on Project Writing”. The target this time would be early careers researchers, e.g. researchers who got their PhD within the last 6 months. The School would offer them: an overview of specific European calls (e.g., MSCAs, ERC Stg etc.), workshops on proposal writing and – possibly and without losing sight of interdisciplinary perspectives – some specific sessions dedicated to disciplines (Life Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities, Physical Sciences and Engineering). The School could be held both online or as a 2/3-day face-to-face meeting. The online mode would allow a higher participation rate (i.e., the School could be open or open previous registration to all 4EU+ researchers belonging to the targeted group) and would be more easily replicable and hence sustainable (no funding required). On the other hand, a face-to-face School would have the added value of creating networks and of having committed participants. Participation would in fact be subject to an internal selection from each partner university (e.g., a number of participants for each discipline could be decided for each university). The in-person modality would require funding for the hosting organisation (each university could be in turn be the host of the School), for external invited speakers and for travel and accommodation (both for participants and officers).

¹ The topics in parenthesis are the ones which potentially could overlap with other TRAIN4EU WP (e.g., WP4 and WP5). A promising possibility would be to combine efforts and organise joint initiatives among WPs.

In the Area of Transformation of organizing dedicated thematic events – especially related to the thematic cases and cross-thematic case selected by our WP1 Team (see D1.1. / M6 & D1.2 / M14) – a series of info-days on HE calls and exchange/networking event. The details are presented in the next section as this pilot action was implemented on November 8, 2022.

Covering all three Areas of Transformation a possible pilot action was designed inspired by of some partner university's best practices. The focus of this pilot action would a specific call, namely the MSCA Post-doctoral Fellowships, and it would be sub-articulated in three related but distinct initiatives.

Firstly, a “4EU+ Supervisors Academy” whose targeted group would be potential supervisors – hence, senior researchers. The Academy's aim would be to train potential supervisors on MSCA fellows' supervision. To grant and facilitate senior researchers' participation, the modality would be an online academy, which could be freely accessible or open subject to pre-registration to the initiative. The online mode would ensure the feasibility and sustainability of the action (no funding necessary).

Secondly, the first action would be complemented by the organisation of thematic masterclasses for potential applicants to the post-doctoral fellowships. The masterclasses would focus on how to write a proposal, how to find a supervisor and how to prepare an application. These could be held in person, online or in a hybrid modality (i.e., possibility to participate remotely for those who cannot attend in person). Depending on the format decided, the participation/application procedure to the masterclasses could vary. Especially, for the hybrid and in-person masterclasses, a pre-selection of participants may result necessary.

Participants could be selected based on two criteria: 4EU+ potential applicants who intend to apply for MSCA fellowships at another 4EU+ University; external potential applicants intending to apply to one 4EU+ University. In the latter case, a decision should be made *ex ante* to avoid future unbalances across 4EU+ Universities – e.g., deciding how many places per university to reserve for external potential applicants.

The table below reports schematically the pilot actions just described.

Area of transformation	Action	Target	Content	Modality	Participation	Funding
Training on emerging topics/ transversal skills	Series of 3/5 sessions on selected topics	Entire 4EU+ community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4EU+ early career and senior researchers 4EU+ research support officers 	On emerging topics, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foreign interference, export control/dual use/data security Research assessment Gender in research (Open Science) (Citizen Science) 	Online	Open	Not necessary
Training / Masterclass focus on EU funding	"4EU+ school on project writing"	Early career researchers Max 1/2 years after PhD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview of specific calls (ERC StG, MSCAs) Proposal writing Common parts and then breakdown per disciplines (Life Sciences, SSH, PE?) 	Plan A: in person 2/3 days	Possible Internal selection at each university. Added value: creating network; commitment of participants.	In person: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding for organisation, external speakers Funding for travel and accommodation (participants, officers) Online: Not necessary
				Plan B: Online - shorter	Open/Open with registration. Added value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> More participants shorter 	
Exchanges/ Partnerships	Info-day on calls + exchange sessions <i>Net4Res – Networking events for the 4EU+ researchers' community.</i>	Senior researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flagships Broader 4EU+ community 	Pilot Thematic case Green Deal/Sustainability. Cross case: Interdisciplinarity. Presentation on available EU call Breakout rooms for meetings among interested participants	Online	Open; preliminary collection of interest	Not necessary

			Researchers sign up prior to the meeting to selected areas/parallel sessions			
MSCA Post-doctoral Fellowships	“4EU+ Supervisors Academy”	Supervisors (senior researchers)	Specific training for supervisors on MSCA fellows’ supervision “know-how”	Online	Open/Open with pre-registration	Not necessary
	Thematic Masterclasses	Potential applicants to post-doctoral fellowships	Masterclass on how to write the proposal	Two-day in person meeting	Internal selection of X participants. (Depending on the format, e.g., if online more participants). - <i>Applicants from 4EU+ universities</i> applying for another. - <i>External applicants applying for a 4EU+ university</i> (avoiding unbalances; possibly a number of reserved places per university)	It depends on the format
				Hybrid		
				Online		
“Researchers dating – matchmaking” between postdocs and supervisors	Supervisors and applicants	Presentations; exchange sessions	Online	Open/Open previous collection of interest	Not necessary (if online)	

4. Net4Res

The first pilot action selected for implementation was the one related to the Exchange/Partnerships area of transformation. More specifically, the organization of a meeting combining an informative session on calls and more structured networking and exchange sessions. The targeted group was the 4EU+ Researchers' Community and, in particular, the meeting was planned as a first step towards developing synergies with 4EU+ Flagships (**Target**).

The meeting was thought as possibly the first of a series of similar meetings called “**Net4Res**” (**Networking 4 Researchers**). Each one would in fact be dedicated to European calls and funding opportunities related to different relevant topics and research areas (e.g., Sustainability, Green Transitions, Digital Transformation, Artificial Intelligence etc.).

4.1 Net4Res – Green Transitions

Sustainability/Green Deal was decided to be the first thematic focus, being one of the two thematic cases analyzed and in-depth assessed by WP1 (see D1.1. /M6 & D1.2 /M14). The meeting was planned as an online meeting (**Modality**): despite the added value of having face-to-face networking meetings, the online modality was deemed more appropriate to allow more researchers to join from all our member universities. Also, being the event considered as the first of a possible series, the online mode ensured that the Net4Res initiative would be non-demanding in terms of funding (**Funding**).

The **Net4Res -Green Transition** was held on November 8, 2022 (from 2pm to 5pm). Researchers interested to participate were asked to register by filling in an online form by the 31st of October 2022.

The aim of this type of pilot action, as anticipated, was twofold: first, to provide 4EU+ researchers with a platform to meet and exchange and, secondly, to provide them with information and support on upcoming funding opportunities related to Sustainability/Green Deal and with a focus on Horizon Europe (**Content**). Therefore, the event was set up as comprising a General Session (45 mins) and following Parallel Sessions (1:30 h).

The General Session included:

- A brief welcoming and introduction to the Net4Res Initiative and TRAIN4EU Project by Elena Del Giorgio (4EU+ GS, UMIL)
- *Workshop: Introduction to Horizon Europe, how to read a work programme and upcoming calls* by Torben Høpck Hansen (UCPH)

The Parallel Sessions were breakout rooms where researchers had the opportunity to briefly present their research expertise and projects, exchange ideas and find potential partners for research collaborations. Parallel Rooms were in fact as many as the following **areas**:

- Agriculture - Animals
- Agriculture - Plants
- Biodiversity
- Circular Economy and Bioeconomy sectors
- CO2 Storage and Conversion
- Food and Food Systems
- Governance and Regulation
- Green Transition Landuse Communities

Researchers, when registering to the event through the online form, were asked to express their interest for one of the above listed area, so that as organizers of the meeting we could monitor and approximately foresee the attendance to each Parallel Sessions (e.g., if zero registrations arrived for an area, the corresponding Parallel Room would have been canceled etc.).

Prior to the meeting, participants were invited to fill in a **template** (see Annex I) that the WP1 Team prepared to facilitate researchers in homogeneously presenting their research activities and interests. Each researcher's presentation should last 2-4 minutes (depending on the number of participants in that Parallel Room) and researchers from the same lab/team were kindly asked to fill in just one template and prepare one joint presentation. Researchers, after the meeting, were also invited to send the WP1 Team their presentations, considering the future possibility of creating a sort of 4EU+ repository available to all 4EU+ researchers and research support offices.

For each Parallel Room a moderator was assigned among experts from each of our universities (in total, 9 experts were finally involved). They were in charge of coordinating and moderating researchers' presentations and the possible follow-up discussion.

The meeting's design mirrors a longtime best practice at UCPH, which periodically organizes this sort of informative and networking meetings for its internal researchers. This is why the technical assistance and support before and during the meeting was kindly supplied by an UCPH IT expert, who had been in charge of:

- Creating the link to the meeting (platform used: Zoom);
- Assigning participants to their selected Parallel Rooms;
- Creating the breakout rooms (i.e. Parallel Sessions) and monitoring them during the meeting (e.g., guide researchers in/our from a breakout rooms)

4.2 Dissemination of the event

The dissemination of **the Net4Res-Green Transitions** event took place at multiple levels and it involved two key steps:

- The preparation of the "Save-the-date and register". This step included an interface with 4EU+ Communication colleagues to design the save-the-date webpage (see Annex II) and decide the publicisation strategy on 4EU+ website and social media; the preparation of an online registration form where researchers were asked to provide their relevant details (Name, Surname, Affiliation, Position, Department/Faculty, Area of interest)
- The writing of the pre-meeting e-mail to send out to registered participants with the following information and material: template and instructions to prepare presentations and for the Parallel Sessions; link to the event and instructions to access the online meeting; final agenda.

The multiple levels of dissemination came at play in the first of the mentioned steps. Firstly, the event was publicized at the 4EU+ level through the publication of a "Save-the-date and register" on the 4EU+ website on September 30, 2022 – more than one month before the event and allowing researchers a 30-day window to register. The event was publicized through a banner on 4EU+ homepage and the [link](#) was shared on 4EU+ social media profiles (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook).

Secondly, the WP1 Team reached out to all Flagship Programme Committees to circulate the "Save-the-date" and link to the event's 4EU+ webpage. This was deemed an important step toward the building of bridges between 4EU+ projects. Also, as Interdisciplinarity was individuated as the cross-

cutting area of transformation, all flagships were contacted notwithstanding the focus of the event was on Sustainability and Green Transitions.

Last but not least, each university exploited its standard internal dissemination procedures and channels. For example, through research support offices' mailing lists, by reaching out to departments/faculties research support offices, by reaching out to researchers and professor already involved in WP1 activities (e.g., interviews), by sharing the event on institutional social media profiles.

Finally, colleagues from UG (University of Geneva), were contacted and invited to circulate the event to their researchers, being by then a full member of the 4EU+ alliance. They did not participate in the TRAIN4EU Swafs Project, as they were not a member of 4eu+ when the consortium was formed.

4.3 Outcomes and evaluation of the pilot action

Registered participants amounted to **152 researchers**. The table below shows registrations by University.

CU	UCPH	UHEI	UG	UMIL	SU	UW
9	22	9	5	70	11	26

The attendance's peak to the meeting was of **54 researchers** (moderators, IT support and organizers not counted). The table below shows attendance by University.

CU	UCPH	UHEI	UG	UMIL	SU	UW
6	4	3	3	31	3	3

The general attendance rate, therefore, turned out to be of 36%. Such a discrepancy between registrations and attendances implied some imbalances in the participation to different Parallel Rooms: while some were fairly crowded (6 to 9 researchers), others only hosted two researchers. In such cases, the moderator of the session gave the researchers two options. After presenting themselves – through the standard template, if made available by the researcher- they could either ask the moderator for more tailored advice and support on HE calls or decide to join another breakout room, where the attendance rate was higher and the exchange and discussion more easily kept lively and ongoing (e.g., the most popular areas were Agriculture-Animals and Food and Food Systems).

Another imbalance that emerged was the different registration and attendance rates per University. UMIL's participation rates alone amounted to 46% of total registrations and 57% of final attendees.

Following up on the meeting and reflecting on how to re-propose this kind of initiative to the 4EU+ researchers' community in the future, also based on received feedback, the WP1 Team took stock of success factors and emerging challenges.

Overall, the event was considered successful from many points of view: the initial interest highlighted by the number of registrations was high and whilst some attendants to the event were already involved in 4EU+, others had only superficially heard of it. The event thus contributed in making 4EU+ activities more visible and known within partner institutions increasing the bases for collaborations among partners. Feedback received by participants, moreover, were positive. Especially, the General Session's workshop Introduction to Horizon Europe, how to read a work programme and upcoming calls was highly participated and retained as very helpful from researchers.

The idea of further developing training of this kind, possibly targeted per level of career/expertise thus emerged (i.e., joint training for early career researchers as included in the above table). Also, participants in the parallel sessions provided appreciative feedback only wishing for more participation from all institutions and for further occasions for exchange.

WP1 Team also singled out some specific challenges and explanations for discrepancies in attendance:

- organizational factors: as already stressed in D1.1. (M6) and D1.2. (M14) our universities are marked by important differences in the way in which research services are organized internally (e.g., level of centralization/decentralization, organization of research support of faculties/departments, type of internal communication flows, services which are offered). In more decentralized universities with multiple layers of support, dissemination from the central level to the Faculty/departmental one might be more difficult resulting in probably only partial advertisement about the event. In more centralized structure this problem might be more easily circumvented. In the case of UMIL, for example, a highly centralized university, the standard procedure adopted was to reach out to the entire researchers' community through an e-mail signed by the Vice Rector for Research.
- EU funding: again, as already outlined in previous deliverables while analyzing funded projects under H2020 at each 4EU+ partner institutions (Horizon Europe results are also being monitored), our universities exhibited different numbers, with the high availability of national funding (often marked by easier access in terms of procedures and success rates) in some cases playing a role in not incentivizing the participation to proposals for EU funding in collaborative projects.
- topic chosen: whilst 4EU+ universities are all comprehensive and cover each a wide range of research areas, not all partners have the same strengths and capacity in all disciplines. This was also the case of sustainability which, whilst being a very broad and interdisciplinary area, is typically tackled in specific Faculties/departments (i.e. agriculture, engineering, economy, political sciences, law) not necessarily present in all universities or not of the same magnitude.
- 4EU+ embedding: the embedding of the Alliance activities, especially within very large comprehensive universities such as ours, indeed, takes time and when the event was organized, a year ago, it is plausible that still segments of involved universities were not aware of the opportunities provided by collaborations within the Alliance.

Such lessons learnt were taken into careful consideration by the WP1 Team leading to some adjustments not only in the above list of possible pilot actions but also in the timing for implementation of further actions. It which was paused to 1) fix first emerging issues 2) align with initiatives promoted centrally by the 4EU+ Alliance (internally funded Calls; new 4EU+ strategy; launch of Grant Support Service. See paragraph 6) to grant actual feasibility and sustainability of the actions.

The organizational challenges encountered, for instance, stimulated WP1 members in the subsequent months to involve more systematically, internally to institutions, research managers working also at the departmental and Faculty level. Such efforts resulted in an enlarged WP1 meeting organized in April and described in the next paragraph.

5. Exchanging with other Alliances: emerging shared opportunities and challenges

The outcomes of Net4Res as well as the reflections on the designing of other pilot actions were not only discussed internally to WP1 but were shared on different occasions with other Alliances. In particular, TRAIN4EU WP1 Team actively participated in two in person meetings together with representatives from other European University Alliances organized precisely with the view of setting up durable networks for exchange.

The first meeting [“Research Management in the European University Alliances”](#) was hosted by University of Palermo (Italy, 20 February 2023), member university of the Forthem Alliance, and was organized in collaboration with the [Italian Research Managers and Administrators \(RMA\) Network](#). The Alliances which contributed to the meeting by showcasing their best practices as well as emerging challenges in setting up joint research management activities were Forthem Alliance, CIVICA, Unite!, 4EU+, Una Europa, respectively represented by their Italian member university: University of Palermo, Bocconi University, Polytechnic of Turin, University of Milan and University of Bologna. More than 50 RMAs participated in the meeting, discussing also the way ahead to further develop actions and initiatives within and across Alliances at national and European level.

The second meeting [“Research Management in European Alliances: Fostering Institutional Transformation”](#) was hosted by Bocconi University (Italy, 25 May 2023) and similarly organized in collaboration with the Italian Research Managers and Administrators (RMA) Network. The meeting was designed as coherent continuation of the previous one, as it allowed a transition from a national to a European perspective. The role of research management and support was addressed both through the European lens (e.g., the ERA Action 17) and within the European University Alliances context. The Alliances which contributed and were represented to the meeting were CIVICA, Forthem Alliance, Unite!, 4EU+, Una Europa, SEA-EU, EUt+, TORCH, ECIU, AURORA.

Additionally, most members of WP1 Team, jointly with colleagues from the Grant Offices of 4EU+ member institutions, attended the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA) annual Conference in Prague (24-26 of April 2023) which also included specific panels and posters on Alliances’ activities.

Immediately following the EARMA Conference, a meeting of WP1 extended Team took place on the 27th of April 2023 at Charles University precisely to jointly take stock of WP1 progress and plan future pilot actions also considering the outcomes of the networking and exchange activities occurred prior and during the Conference. The meeting allowed for an increased participation by 4EU+ member institutions representatives as colleagues from partner universities who were already travelling to Prague for the Conference could also and more easily join the meeting. Overall attendants were 20. The extended meeting was thus an occasion to enlarge our RMAs internal network and to discuss the next steps ahead (also beyond the TRAIN4EU project’s timeline) to ensure future joint collaboration and learning across our Alliance and among Alliances. In this vein, the list of possible WP1 pilot actions was refined.

The meetings organized jointly with other Alliances and the Italian Research Managers and Administrators (RMA) Network and the EARMA Conference, revealed important for fostering networking and exchange of best practice and for building up durable collaborations which, indeed, continue, both formally and informally. In terms of outcomes, moreover, they also led to the identification of strikingly similar challenges especially in enhancing collaboration among researchers

across partner institutions. This often irrespectively of the size and nature of the Alliance (more thematically focused or composed by comprehensive universities). Most of these challenges were summarized in a poster prepared by the EARMA Thematic Group “European Universities Alliances”, featuring also 4EU+ as member of the group, displayed at the EARMA Conference. (Annex III).

First of all, problems with aligning activities in education funded under Erasmus+ projects and R&I due to different timing, framework and type of financial support were commonly highlighted. Another barrier which was singled out concerned the role and professional profile of RMAs. Such profiles, indeed, are still underrepresented and underrecognized both at national and European levels despite the growing centrality and complexity of the type of expert support given by RMAs in strengthening inter and intra universities cooperation (see ERA Action 17).

A further and crucial common challenge related to the identification of the possible actions, instruments and above all incentives to successfully enhance collaboration among researchers within Alliances. This also beyond the SwafS project and considering the uncertainty regarding future funding for supporting the R&I dimension of Alliances as well as the parallel workload required to institutions to implement and sustain activities. Albeit developing different types of approaches and pilot actions to foster research collaboration, indeed, Alliances representatives stressed difficulties in rapidly incentivizing and engaging researchers in joint projects and activities. The need for time and further financial support for fostering capacity building and cooperation, thus, emerged as fundamental.

6. Anchoring WP1 activities within the 4EU+ Alliance structures and activities

The awareness of the crucial importance of financial support to R&I collaborations and of the need for an integrated, holistic approach to funding aimed at better aligning education and R&I activities, was precisely at the basis of the launch, in April 2023, of [two internal 4EU+ Calls](#), directly funded from the budgets of 4EU+ member universities: Visiting Professorships and SEED4EU+. Between M25 and M32, the WP1 Team was consulted and some members directly involved in the planning and implementation of the latter.

The aims of SEED4EU+ were to: broaden the engagement of the communities of all 4EU+ universities in creating and developing One Comprehensive Research-Intensive European University; provide seed funding for the implementation of novel ideas within and across education, research and innovation as well as other areas such as societal engagement and citizen science; contribute to the general sustainability of cooperation within 4EU+. Applicants could be researchers and academics starting from postgraduate level 1 and affiliated to any 4EU+ universities with proposals being submitted by teams including participants from minimum three 4EU+ member universities participating in the call (proposals including four or more 4EU+ member universities are strongly encouraged). Projects could run for a period of up to 12 months and the maximum funding available per project was 50,000 euros.

The SEED4EU+ call received 42 applications from teams involving altogether more than 400 academics and students. Out of these, finally 19 projects were selected for funding. Over half of the applications involved more than three 4EU+ member universities. It is interesting to note that among the “project category” which could be chosen— education, research, innovation, social outreach, 4EU+ community building (multiple choice was possible) – that of research (often combined with education) was the most flagged.

The process and outcomes of the Call are currently being assessed at the 4EU+ level with members of the WP1 Team involved in the process. The 4EU+ view is that of launching further internal Calls. Their design might vary, especially to take into consideration the need to strengthen R&I activities vis-à-vis the lack of external funding after the end of TRAIN4EU.

WP1 Team members were also substantially involved in the drafting of the BRIDGE4EU proposal (101136850) in response to the HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-03-01 Call. The proposal, submitted in April 2023, as those submitted by several other Alliances, was finally not retained for funding.

As outlined in previous deliverable, however, WP1 activities anchoring within the 4EU+ structures is also being carried on through a strong contribution to the development of the former Virtual Development Office (VDO) already envisaged in the first 4EU+ Erasmus+ project and confirmed in the second one (1CORE). The VDO has recently being further structured and presented to the 4EU+ community under a new name: [4EU+ Grant Support Service \(GSS\)](#). The GSS combines services provided by local grant support offices at all universities of the 4EU+ Alliance with a comprehensive selection of relevant calls from the Alliance, the EU level as well as other funders on the R&I side. It builds on the network of RMAs which has broadened and consolidated through the joint work in WP1. The service is currently coordinated at the University of Heidelberg by UHEI WP1 member.

Finally, the 4EU+ Governance has started in 2023 a strategic process which will lead at the end of 2024 to the launch of the new 4EU+ Strategy 2025-2035 (the exact timeframe of the Strategy is being finalized). Research will be one of the four building blocks of the Strategy. The current draft has been circulated and discussed at Governance, Flagships, Working Groups and TRAIN4EU Steering Committee meetings during the Annual Meeting 2023 which was held in Milan on 7-9 November 2023. The feedback gathered during the AM is currently being discussed and will lead to a new draft. A broader consultation process will then start in Q1 of 2024.

The WP1 Team is contributing to the process by refining the designing of pilot actions to possibly be part of the strategic actions and by finalizing a report on WP1 outcomes and lessons learnt as part of the feedback to the Research building block.

Annex I: Net4Res- Green Transitions – Researchers’ template

 Insert Photo	Net4Res-Green Transitions 8 November 2022	4eu+
<p style="text-align: center;">General & Contact info</p> <p>Name(s) & Surname(s):</p> <p>Affiliation(s):</p> <p>Position(s):</p> <p>E-mail:</p> <p>Other contacts:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Research Area & Expertise</p>	

<p style="text-align: center;">Main Projects & Research Activities</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Research Networks</p>	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Infrastructures & Facilities</p>	
<p>Horizon Europe Calls – Potential interest or ongoing application(s)</p>		4eu+

Annex II: Net4Res Save-the-date 4EU+ webpage

Below a preview of the Net4Res-Green Transition save-the-date 4EU+ webpage still available at the following link: <https://4euplus.eu/4EU-728.html>.

Net4Res – Networking events for the 4EU+ researchers' community: Green Transitions

Join the pilot 4EU+ researchers' meeting dedicated to networking, exchange and Horizon Europe funding opportunities related to Green Deal/Sustainability.

Save the date and register!

8 November 2022, 14:00 - 17:00

Net4Res – Networking events for the 4EU+ researchers' community: Green Transitions

Join the pilot 4EU+ researchers' meeting dedicated to networking, exchange and Horizon Europe funding opportunities related to Green Deal/Sustainability

Annex III – EARMA Conference – EARMA Thematic Group “European Universities Alliances” Poster

How RMAs are helping to build the

European Universities Alliances

The EARMA Thematic Group working on the integration of research and innovation topics in European Ualliances (EUAs): challenges, first results and perspectives.

Our best practices and success stories

- CHARM-EU**: Best Practices to decrease local barriers to Open Science
- ENLIGHT**: Repository of Good Practices on Research Impact
- Ulyssseus**: A common R&I agenda and action plan
- film.eu**: Online training materials on artistic research
- AURORA**: SDG Research Dashboard; Interactive map on sharable Research Resources
- SEA EU**: Joint Research Potential Database
- una.europa**: Cluster expert groups on research coordination, Infrastructures, career and culture, private-public sectors, open research, citizens engagement
- forthem.**: Joint Research Services and Policy Office; Book on Good Practices in R&I
- eur+**: Joint Institutional repository in Open Aaire; Joint Open Access Academic Press;
- 4eu+**: 4 thematic Flagships; Legal Entity Established; Development of a Virtual Development Office

Who we are?

The initial contributors to this thematic group are:

FORTHem Alliance: [Birkle, Nicole \(FT\) general-secretary@fortem-alliance.eu](mailto:Birkle.Nicole@fortem-alliance.eu); **FilmEU:** [Daithi Mac Siuthigh Daithi.MacSiuthigh@iadt.ie](mailto:Daithi.Mac.Siuthigh@iadt.ie); **UNA EUROPA/UNA RESIN:** [Hideko Matsuo, Hideko.Matsuo@kuleuven.be](mailto:Hideko.Matsuo@kuleuven.be); **Sea-EU:** [Marie Calleja marie.calleja@uam.edu.mx](mailto:Marie.Calleja@uam.edu.mx); **Aurora Alliance:** [Ignasi Salvado Estiñé ignasi.salvado@urv.cat](mailto:Ignasi.Salvado@urv.cat); [Maite Najero Garcia maite.najero@urv.cat](mailto:Maite.Najero@urv.cat); **ENLIGHT:** [Dirk De Cremer Dirk.DeCremer@UGent.be](mailto:Dirk.DeCremer@UGent.be); **CharmEU Alliance:** [Dotis Alexander Dotis.Alexander@uclouvain.be](mailto:Dotis.Alexander@uclouvain.be); **Ulyssseus:** [Melanie Rivers melanie@uclouvain.be](mailto:Melanie.Rivers@uclouvain.be); **4eu+:** [Eleanora Zuolo eleanora.zuolo@univ-paris-saclay.fr](mailto:Eleanora.Zuolo@univ-paris-saclay.fr); **Eur+:** [John Donovan john.donovan@tcd.ie](mailto:John.Donovan@tcd.ie)

What are our major objectives?

- To exchange best practices, project experiences/outputs and boost mutual learning.
- To create an expert support group on research management and development of integrated R&I agendas.
- To promote equal importance of education, R&I and societal responsibility within the EUAs, and jointly stand up for robust funding to deliver on these missions.
- To provide opportunities for alliances to contribute to the transformation agenda of the ERA.

What are the common R&I challenges the Alliances are facing?

- (Dis)integrated vision of education, research and innovation.
- Different approaches by European (DG EAC and DG RTD) and National Public Agencies to the Alliances.
- Collaborative vs competitive support to the researchers across the Alliances.
- Lack of incentives for researchers to participate in institutional transformation projects; 'what is it in for them?'
- Under-resourcing of the university staff (including RMAs) to effectively engage in the Alliances.
- How to bring researchers together for joint research project applications, when the EUAs mainly focus on student and mobility issues.
- The EUAs are addressing manifold challenging topics all at the same time.
- More efficient communication activities to increase our internal/external visibility; 'how to sell it to stakeholders?'

What is needed to progress the R&I agenda?

- A streamlined and strategic policy approach towards supporting universities as pivotal actors across the whole ERA, with dedicated funding streams.
- Investment in more targeted instruments to incentivise and support bottom-up research collaboration to strengthen ties between academics across departments, institutions, and countries to forge a vibrant pan-European academic community.
- Support for a true European Excellence Initiative that provides support to higher education institutions in all parts of the ERA, along with continued commitment to the widening dimension.
- Stronger synergies between EU funding programmes, notably Erasmus+, Horizon Europe and Digital Europe, and National funding programmes, with a view to enabling universities as drivers of both an innovative, globally competitive, and attractive Europe.
- Upskilling of research support professionals to deal with the complexity of inter-institutional collaboration

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